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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Effervescent Based Gastro Retentive Floating Tablets of Nifedipine

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to develop and assess gastro-retentive floating tablets of nifedipine, designed to sustain drug release for up to 12 hour. The formulation utilize natural polymers, including xanthan gum and gum tragacanth employing a direct compression method. An effervescent gas generating agent, consisting of sodium bicarbonate, was incorporated to facilitate the floating capability of the tablets. The prepared gastroretentive floating tablets underwent a series of evaluation, including drug-excipient compatibility studies, weight variation, thickness, hardness, content uniformity, in vitro buoyancy assessments, and in vitro drug release studies conducted in 0.1N HCL over a 12-hour period .The finding of this investigation demonstrate the significant potential of the nifedipine floating system as a viable alternative to tradition dosage forms and other sustained-release formulation .Additionally, the study highlights the efficacy of the employed polymers in drug delivery. The blend of all the formulation showed good flow properties such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, The prepared tablets were shown good post compression parameters such as hardness, thickness, friability, precent drug content, weight variation tests and they passed aal the quality control evaluation parameters as per I.P limits. Sodium bicarbonate concentration is optimize by trails. we found 20% is optimum to obtain required floating lag time (4.4 min) and total floating time(7hours).

INTRODUCTION

Oral administration represent the most adaptable, convenient, and widely utilized method for delivering drugs intended for systemic effect.

Recently, there has been a growing interest in oral controlled release drug delivery system within the pharmaceutical sector, aimed at enhancing therapeutic benefits such as ease of administration. Patient adherence, and formulation flexibility.^{2,3} A

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controlled drug delivery system that ensure an extended residence time in the stomach is particularly advantageous for medication that are locally active in the stomach, have a narrow absorption window within the gastrointestinal tract, are primarily absorb in the stomach and upper gastrointestinal tract, are unstable in the intestinal or colonic environment disrupt normal colonic microbiota and demonstrate low solubility at elevated pH levels. The retention of solid dosage forms in the stomach can be achieved through floating systems, which allow gastro-retentive dosage forms to remain in the gastric region for several hours, thereby significantly extending the gastric residence time of the drugs. This prolonged gastric retention enhance bioavailability, minimize drug wastage and improves the solubility of drug that are less soluble in high pH condition. Gastroretention facilities better availability of new products with appropriate therapeutic efficacy, offering substantial advantages for patients. Nifedipine, a selective calcium channel blocker, is utilized in the treatment of vasospastic angina, chronic stable angina, hypertension and reynaud`s phenomenon. It exhibits poor water solubility and high permeability, classified as Class II drug according to the biopharmaceutics classification system.^{13 17 1} The oral absorption of nifedipine is characterized as uniform, rapid and completed with a bioavailability of approximately 45-50% and an elimination half-life pf 2 to 4hours, necessitating dosing two to three times daily for many patients, which often results in non compliance. The development of floating (effervescent technology) nifedipine tablets involved the direct compression of natural polymers and the resulting formulation were assessed for a number of physico-chemical properties. These administration method helps to improve the sustained delivery of drugs with an absorption window in a specific area of the gastrointestinal tract by keeping them in the

stomach. By constantly releasing the medication before it enters the absorption window, these system contribute to the best possible bioavailability, Additionally, the formulation is an economical procedure.^{12 15 16}

Drug Profile:

Drug name: Nifedipine

Chemical structure:

Chemical Name : 3,5-dimethyl 2,6-dimethyl-4-(2-nitrophenyl)-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate.

Chemical Formula : C₁₇H₁₈NO₆

Molecular Weight :346.335g/mol.

Controlled drug delivery systems :

Regulate medication delivery methods in order to maintain the length of therapeutic activity, target the distribution of the medication to a tissue, and or control the rate of drug as administration, controlled drug delivery systems have been created. In the medicine is given in repeated doses since nifedipine undergoes hepatic metabolism, which result in a very poor bioavailability (40-56%) and short half-life(2hour). Nifedipine is therefore best prepared as intragastric floating

tablets to increase its bioavailability and lower its dosage.^{21 28 31}

Floating system :

Floating mechanism since their bulk density is lower than that of gastric fluids, floating drug delivery system (FDDS) float in the stomach without slowing down the rate of gastric emptying. While the body is floating on the content of the stomach, the medication is gradually removed from the system at the appropriate rate.^{22 26 4} Drug release is followed by the emptying of the stomachs residual system.

METHODOLOGY:

Formulation of Nifedipine Floating Tablets:

In the presence of sodium bicarbonate was utilized as an effervescent gas-generating agent. At the

optimized concentration of sodium bicarbonate(15mg), floating granules of nifedipine were prepared using various concentration of different grades of polymers, as detailed in Table 1. The drug and all other components were individually passed through a sieve #60 and thoroughly mixed by triturating for up to 15 minutes.^{7 8} The resulting powder mixture was lubricated with talc. The powder was then compressed using a direct compression method with a 7mm tablet punch. Six distinct formulation of tablets were created with varying concentration of different polymers. Based on subsequent physicochemical evaluation and in vitro drug release studies, the optimal formulation were identified.^{5 6}

Formulation development of tablets :

Table 1. The Formulation Of different formulation F1-F6(mg/tablet)

Formulation code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Nifedipine	20	0	0	20	20	20
Xanthan Gum	20	40	60	-	-	-
Gum Tragacanth	-	-	-	20	40	60
NaHCO ₃ (20%)	40	40	40	40	40	40
Mag. Sterate (2%)	4	4	4	4	4	4
Talc (2%)	4	4	4	4	4	4
MCC pH102	112	92	72	112	92	72
Total weight	200	200	200	200	200	200

Analytical Method:

Standard calibration curve of Nifedipine was taken in simulated Gastric fluid (PH1.2) at 238nm.^{9 10}

Table 1: Observation for graph of nifedipine in 0.1 N HCL

Conc. (µg/ml)	Absorbance
0	0
1	0.121
2	0.245

3	0.371
4	0.504
5	0.614

Figure 1: Standard graph of nifedipine in 0.1N HCL

Drug – excipient compatibility studies:

Fourier transform – infrared spectroscopy

Figure 2: nifedipine

Figure 3: Magnesium stearate

Figure 4: Gum tragacanth

Figure 5: Sodium Bicarbonate

Figure 6: microcrystalline cellulose

Figure 7: talc

From the FTIR data it was evident that the drug and excipients does not have any interactions. Hence they were compatible .

Precompression Parameters:

The quality of tablet, once formulated according to established guidelines, is primarily influenced by the physiochemical properties of the blends, which are assessed in accordance with pharmacopoeia standards prior to compression.^{11 14 18}The formulation powder blends undergo evaluation for both bulk and tapped density, from which the compressibility index and hausner`s ratio are derived. Additionally ,the flow characteristics of the powder blend are determined through the angle of repose.^{19 20}

Bulk Density:

Density is defined as the mass per unit volume. bulk density refers to the mass of the powder divided by its bulk volume, expressed in gm/cm³. The bulk density of a powder is largely influenced by the factors such as particle size distribution, particle shape, and the tendency of particles to clump together, the calculation for bulk density is given by formula : bulk density = M/V₀, where M represents the weight of the sample and V₀ denotes the apparent volume of the powder^{23 24}. At 10 gm powder blend was sieved and placed into a dry 20mL cylinder without compaction . The powder was carefully leveled without compressing it, and the unsettled apparent volume, V₀, was recorded.²⁷

Tapped Density:

Following procedure for measuring bulk density, the cylinder containing the sample was subjected to tapping using a mechanical tapped density tester, which deliver 100 taps per minute. This process was continued until the difference between consecutive measurement was less than 2%. The

tapped volume, V, was then measured to the nearest graduated unit.^{36 41} Tapped density was calculated in gm per L using the formula: Tapped Density=M/V, where M is the weight of the sample and V is the tapped volume of the powder.³⁰

Measures of Powder Compressibility:

The Compressibility index, also known as Carr`s index, quantifies the tendency of a powder to be compressed. Materials with poorer flow characteristics typically exhibit stronger interparticle interaction, resulting in a more significant disparity between bulk and tapped densities.^{43 33} The variation are evident in the compressibility index, which is determined using the formula: Carr`s index= [(tap – b)/tap]x 100, where b represent Bulk density and Tao denotes Tapped density.

The Angle of Repose:

The frictional force present in loose powder can be quantified by the angle of repose. The fixed funnel method was utilized for this measurement. A funnel was positioned with its tips at a specific height(h) above a sheet of graph paper placed on a level surface. The powder blend was carefully poured through the funnel until the peak of the conical pile made contact with the funnel`s tip. The radius(r) of the base of the conical pile was then measured. The angle of repose is calculated as follow: $\text{Tan}\theta = h/r$, where h is the height of the cone and r is the radius of the cone`s base.⁴⁴

Post Evaluation Of Prepared Nifedipine Floating Tablets:

The quality control of the prepared tablets was assessed through various tests, including weight variation, tablet thickness, hardness, friability,

assay, in vitro buoyancy, and in vitro drug release studies.

Weight Variation :

A random selection of ten tablets from each batch was weighed individually to determine the average weight.^{32 38 39} The individual weights were then compared to this average, allowing for the calculation of the percentage weight difference, which was subsequently evaluated against USP specification.

Hardness and Friability :

The hardness of the tablets was measured using a Monsanto hardness tester. Ten tablets from each batch were randomly selected for this analysis, and both the mean and standard deviation were calculated. The friability test was performed using a Roche friabilator, where ten tablets were weighed and subjected to a combination of attrition and shock within a plastic chamber that rotates at 25 rpm, dropping the tablets from a height of 6 inches with each revolution.^{34 35 37} After 100 revolutions, the tablets were cleaned of dust and reweighed to calculate the percentage of friability.

Tablet Dimensions :

The thickness and diameter of the tablets were measured with calibrated dial calipers. Three tablets from each formulation were randomly chosen for this measurement, and the dimensions were recorded in millimeters, along with the standard deviations.⁴⁰

Determination of Drug Content:

The drug content of the compression-coated tablets was evaluated by finely powdering ten tablets. An amount of powder equivalent to the weight of one tablet of nifedipine was accurately

weighed and transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask containing 50 mL of water. The mixture was allowed to stand to ensure complete dissolution of the drug, after which the volume was adjusted to 100 mL with water.⁴² The solution was appropriately diluted, and the absorption was measured using a UV visible spectrophotometer. The drug concentration was then determined from the calibration curve.^{45 46}

In vitro Buoyancy Assessments:

The assessment of in vitro buoyancy was conducted by measuring the floating lag time, following the methodology outlined by Rosa et al. Tablets were immersed in a 250 mL beaker containing 200 mL of 0.1 N HCL. The duration taken for the tablet to ascend to the surface and achieve flotation was recorded as the floating lag time (FLT)^{9 5}, while the duration for which the tablet remained buoyant was noted as the total floating time (TFT).

In vitro Dissolution Assessments :

The in vitro dissolution assessment was carried out utilizing a United States Pharmacopeia (USP) type II (paddle) apparatus, operating at a rotational speed of 100 rpm. A total of 900 mL of 0.1 N HCL served as the dissolution medium, with the temperature maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. At predetermined intervals over a 12-hour period, a 5 mL sample was extracted from the dissolution apparatus, and an equivalent volume of prewarmed fresh dissolution medium was added to the volume.^{1 7} The samples were subsequently filtered through Whatman filter paper (40 μ) and diluted to an appropriate concentration with 0.1 N HCL. Absorbance of these solutions was measured at 238 nm using a UV spectrophotometer.^{4 3}

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

This study focuses on nifedipine, a calcium channel blocker commonly prescribed for angina and Raynaud's syndrome. Nifedipine has been identified as a promising candidate for reducing dosing frequency in solid oral controlled-release formulations, thereby enhancing patients' compliance in angina management. Due to its poor solubility in water, efforts were made to enhance the drug's solubility by incorporating various concentrations of natural gums. The aim was to develop gastroretentive floating tablets that would ensure a controlled and sustained release of the medication over an extended period. The preparation of nifedipine floating tablets involved

dry blending of solubility modifiers to enhance the active drug's solubility, along with varying concentrations of different polymers grades, sodium bicarbonate utilizing a direct compression technique.

Precompression Parameters

The angle of repose measurements indicate that the powder blend exhibits favorable flow characteristics. The bulk density of all formulations ranged from 0.48 to 0.55 (gm/mL), further confirming the good flow properties of the powder.

Table 3: Preformulation parameter of powder blend.

Formulation Ratio code	Angle of repose	Bulk density (gm/mL)	Tapped density (gm/mL)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	24.23	0.54	0.65	16.92	1.20
F2	25.11	0.49	0.59	16.94	1.20
F3	26.21	0.51	0.62	17.74	1.17
F4	27.15	0.53	0.65	18.23	1.13
F5	26.08	0.48	0.56	14.28	1.16
F6	25.01	0.53	0.63	15.87	1.18

The results of precompression evaluation parameters are displayed in (Table.3), and all formulations had a tapped density in the range 0.56 to 0.65, indicating that the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all formulations was found to be below 18, indicating that the powder has the good flow properties.

Quality Control Parameters for Tablets

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, content and drug release studies were performed for floating tablets.

Table 4: Post compression parameters for tablets

Formulation codes	Weight variations (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	Floating lag time (min)	Total floating time (h)
F1	198.7	5.2	0.57	3.3	91.43	5.0	4
F2	199.2	5.4	0.58	3.4	90.67	5.7	5
F3	201.2	5.1	0.62	3.2	92.78	5.5	5
F4	200.6	5.5	0.66	3.3	91.01	4.8	6
F5	197.9	5.3	0.59	3.4	93.11	5.2	6
F6	200.4	5.2	0.61	3.2	96.67	4.3	7

The findings from the physiochemical characterizations are presented in Table 4. The thickness of the tablets was assessed using a calibrated dial caliper. The average diameter and thickness of the tablets were consistent across all formulations, with measurements ranging from 3.3 ± 0.156 to 3.4 ± 0.130 mm, respectively. The standard deviation values suggest that all formulations maintained uniform thickness. The average weight for each formulation was documented, revealing consistency within the specification set by the USP. The weight of the tablets varied from 197 to 201mg. All tablets successfully passed the weight variations test, as the percentage weight variation remained within limit of $\pm 2\%$. The hardness of the formulation ranged from 5.25 ± 0.165 to 5.5 ± 0.196 kg/cm². The standard deviation values indicate that the hardness across all formulation was relatively uniform, demonstrating adequate mechanical strength and hardness. The friability values for the prepared tablets are listed in table 3, with results

ranging from 0.57% to 0.66%. All values are below 1%, indicating that the tablets from all formulations exhibits good compactness and sufficient resistance to mechanical shock and abrasion. Content uniformity was assessed for all 6 formulations, revealing that the percent drug content of the tablets ranged from 96.67% to 99.67% for nifedipine.

In Vitro Buoyancy Studies:

All intragastric floating tablet formulations were developed using an effervescent method. Upon immersion in a 0.1 N HCL solution at a Ph 1.2 and a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, all floating effervescent tablets floated immediately and remained buoyant for up to 7 hours without disintegrating. The in vitro buoyancy of the nifedipine tablets was achieved through the use of sodium bicarbonate, ensuring the integrity of matrix was maintained.

At 0 min

After 7 h

Figure 8: The floating position of nifedipine floating tablets in 0.1 N HCL solution at different time intervals.

In Vitro Drug Release Studies :

The xantan gum – prepared formulations had very little retardation capacity, they were disregarded.

The F6 formulation was therefore deemed to be optimal formulation based on the above dissolution results because of its good release (91.98%) over a 7-hours period.

M8 Table 5: dissolution data of nifedipine tablets

Time (hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	44.52	34.23	36.73	13.21	24.76	10.73
2	61.35	41.71	49.08	26.46	37.89	27.91
3	79.01	54.62	61.87	38.96	51.23	36.07
4	81.23	72.36	75.67	58.23	68.29	54.17
5		79.2	84.55	69.08	79.67	71.93
6				86.12	87.88	85.13
7						91.98

Figure 10: In vitro drug release profile of formulation F1-F6**CONCLUSION:**

The objective of developing gastroretentive floating drug delivery systems for nifedipine tablets is to ensure the drug's therapeutic effect lasts for up to 7 hours. These gastro-retentive floating tablets were created using direct compression method, incorporating various natural polymers such as xanthan gum and gum tragacanth. The resulting formulations were

assessed based on several criteria, including drug – excipients compatibility, weight variation, thickness, mass, content uniformity, in vitro buoyancy, and in vitro drug release studies conducted in 0.1N HCL over a period of 7 hours. Leading to the conclusion that formulation F6 exhibited the most favorable results. This study concludes that the gastro-retentive floating system may be an effective approach for the administration of nifedipine.

Figure 11: Comparison Of % Drug Release For 6 Batches Over Time

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